

ceptible genotypes were found in common between the new scale and SES. Ten resistant, no intermediate, and 8 susceptible genotypes were in common between the SES scale and Jackson's scale. Six genotypes (HKR86-403, HKR90-408, HKR90-410, HKR91-438,

RP2633-15-2-5, and Taraori Basmati) found resistant with the new scale had 7.4, 10.0, 9.1, 7.4, 5.3, and 7.3% of infected tillers. These entries were excluded from the resistant category by SES because they just crossed the resistance limit (<5% infected tillers). ■

removed 7 d after oviposition and kept in a container for hatching. The larvae can either be used for experiments or for reinfesting a fresh plot to maintain the colony.

Four separate, overlapping colonies can be maintained by infesting every 4th plot with larvae from a single earlier plot. Alternatively, because moth emergence from each plot occurs over a period of 12-18 d, colonies can be continuously mixed by infesting each new plot with larvae from 2-3 previous plots.

Between August 1994 and January 1996, we reared 4 separate, overlapping YSB colonies for 6-10 generations each, assuring an uninterrupted supply of 200-600 female moths each week. The overall mean number of moths produced and sex ratio (proportion of females among total adults) were 865.1 ± 11.5 and 0.57 ± 0.001 , respectively. Mean developmental time was 39.2 ± 0.04 d and was highly dependent upon seasonal temperatures. Colony performance was measured by total number of moths produced and the sex ratio. The table shows that performance was not correlated with the number of generations a colony had been in culture, indicating that colony performance did not deteriorate over time. In 3 of the 4 colonies, performance was not correlated with age of plants at the time of infestation (range 65-100 d after sowing), indicating that reproductive-stage plants of a wide range of ages were suitable for colony maintenance. ■

A procedure for continuous greenhouse rearing of the yellow stem borer

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Studies of yellow stem borer (YSB), *Scirpophaga incertulas*, are often disrupted because of the great difficulty of rearing this species. We have developed a procedure to maintain colonies of YSB in a greenhouse. This procedure has provided us with a daily supply of adults for our research.

Our greenhouse has a floor space of 56×20 m. The planting area is divided into 16 plots of 15 m^2 . Seedlings of rice variety IR62 are grown and transplanted in each of the plots at 7- to 10-d intervals. Each plot has 11 rows of 32 hills planted at 20×20 -cm spacing. To initiate colonies, adult moths of YSB are collected from the field and caged on plants for oviposition. Neonate larvae hatch from these egg masses and are used to infest the plots at 10-15 larvae hill^{-1} when the plants are 65-100 d old. At this stage of plant growth, each hill

has 12-15 tillers and 4224 tillers are infested in each plot. Four weeks after infestation, the plants are trimmed 40 cm above ground level to facilitate adult moth emergence. Plots of trimmed plants are covered with fine fiberglass mesh to collect adults. Moths are collected every day and caged on 40-d-old potted plants for oviposition. Pieces of leaves with egg masses are

Performance of YSB colonies at IIRRI over time.^a

Colony	Dependent variable	
	Sex ratio	Total adults produced
Colony A (n = 6 generations)		
Generation	0.510	-0.307
Plant age	-0.004	0.119
Colony B1 (n = 10)		
Generation	0.413	-0.364
Plant age	0.896 ^b	0.427
Colony B2 (n = 7)		
Generation	0.903	0.711
Plant age	0.606	0.552
Colony C (n = 8)		
Generation	0.212	-0.329
Plant age	0.260	0.644

^aValues are correlation coefficients. ^bSignificant (P<0.05).